

USING INDEPENDENT STUDY SKILLS IN TEACHING “INTRODUCTION TO LINGUISTIC PRAGMATICS”

A. Shermatov¹

Abstract:

The article presents the importance and role of independent study in the subject of “Introduction to linguistic pragmatics” for master students. The objectives of independent study of this subject and the criteria in order to gain by independent study for master students in the subject of “Introduction to linguistic pragmatics” have been clarified in several cases.

Key words: independent study, task, skills, competencies, teaching, knowledge.

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Independent study is a systematic activity aimed at the formation of theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications based on independent mastering of educational material, assignments of different levels of complexity, creative and independent performance of practical tasks in the audience and outside the audience [6; 21].

The priorities of the systematic reform of higher education in the “Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5847 of October 8, 2019, the process of training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and independent thinking to a qualitatively new level raising, modernization of higher education and development of social sphere and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies as strategic issues. For example, in the Concept, increasing the share of independent study hours, students' independent study, critical and creative thinking, systematic analysis, formation of entrepreneurial skills, introduction of methods and technologies aimed at strengthening competencies in the educational process, directing the educational process to the formation of practical skills, in this regard, to the educational process the task of wide introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies, educational programs and teaching-methodical materials based on international educational standards. Also, it is explained that students can acquire the necessary competencies, creative creativity, research, and logical thinking through independent education, independent work and continuous improvement of their skills.

Usually, any subject is based on independent study. There is no subject that is free of independent study. The role of independent study used in the classes by the teacher to accurately illuminate the nature of the subject being studied is of great importance. It should be noted that an independent study involves master students to work out of the classroom, such as scientific thinking in “Introduction to linguistic pragmatics”, linguistic methods, linguistic theories, linguistic researches and linguistic views relating to “Introduction to

¹ Shermatov Akram Abdukhakimovich, Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

linguistic pragmatics". Independent study helps master students to develop the skills and knowledge of linguistic pragmatics.

There are some objectives to be paid attention in the field of independent study for teaching "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics" classes:

- to review all the features connecting to independent study and teaching process of "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics";
- to update pedagogical and methodological criteria of independent study in "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics";
- to work out modern and innovative methods of teaching for "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics" classes by comparing other fields of linguistics;
- to work out and redesign quality assurance principles in teaching "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics" classes.

The process of independent study contributes to master students' knowledge of "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics" classes and helps to increase for their knowledge by the following features:

- be active and professional master student in research sphere of "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics";
- a master student who is interested in knowing more about in "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics" than is covered in the regular curriculum may propose a research project;
- have an opportunity to continue research process in "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics";
- find additional materials from internet resources and use them;
- useful for the teacher to examine separately independent study objectives, make conclusions, analyze and evaluate them;
- a teacher saves time.

If the above-mentioned features work accurately then by the turn of those, students can gain their knowledge of "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics" by the following characteristics:

- improve their knowledge on "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics" independently;
- developing critical thinking in "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics";
- form practical skills and IS in "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics" classes;
- to have skills of evaluation each other's qualification in "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics" classes.

Educational and QA principles in independent study activities of "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics" classes should observe such conditions as planning lessons and include varied activities and interactions that keep the students busy, using topics and activities that we think will be interesting and effective to the learners, trying to create a sense of community in the course, fixing exact support and other types of aid (to give suggestions, explaining content of the theme, giving additional information on problematic tasks), defining exact assessment criteria on independent study.

At present, new information on scientific and technological developments is mainly derived from the Internet. Therefore, there is a wide spread of radio, telephone, TV and internet. Thus, it is envisaged that teachers will be able to work with the internet more effectively, taking into account the technical knowledge of the students. In this process, not only strong students, but also those who are weaker can participate. Sometimes "poor" students may not be able to demonstrate their knowledge in practical lesson sessions. However, a weak student can have a broader outlook of his or her abilities in an online study system or, in other words, independent study processes. In short, using the online learning

system in an independent study process, first of all, is closely linked to student and teacher collaboration. It is also important to save time on double-sided, save paper based materials. By working online, the student will be able to compare his / her informative knowledge with the materials he / she has received, to have the ability to express his / her own opinions and to enrich his / her knowledge on "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics".

There should be worked out the methodology of evaluation process of independent study in "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics" classes. First of all we should pay to attention in order to evaluate students, the course and teaching processes. It is important to remember that a person can also note how effectively the students communicate in free conversation and group work and how well they use the language in homework composition in the process of evaluating learning [1; 185-190].

One of the key issues is how to develop new mechanisms for evaluating the process of independent study. In addition, the student is not only involved in the workshop hours, but also by online activities (in which the student's opinion, question-answer discussion, academic thinking, ability to think independently and so on), as well as foreign languages, it is desirable to make an unequivocal appraisal by adding oral speech [2; 124].

In the consequence, it would be better that independent study hours of "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics" classes at least (50 %) should be included to teachers' annual academic hours. Independent study processes give us to create a teaching aids connecting to "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics" as well as separately for the lecture hours and practical lessons and give detailed information about them. Besides, it gives a chance for master students in order to make schemes of independent study on learning materials and including assessment design processes. We need professional specialists in the field of "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics" who know not only the theory of this subject but also everything which is connected with "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics" processes and also who can analyze texts as linguistic pragmatics ways. Teachers who teaches "Introduction to linguistic pragmatics" classes can do 30% of all activities but 70% of activities are done by master students (the method of blended learning plays a great role in this process). From the above-mentioned it can be concluded that depending on the topic of the subject, master students should take into consideration the following factors before proceeding to the independent study process:

- getting to know the scientific literature (internet) related to the topic;
- collecting information from additional literature related to the topic;
- analyzing independently the glossary related to the topic;
- prepare for to be given questions related to the topic;
- realizing on time independent study tasks related to the topic on the MOODLE platform;
- individual or collective preparation of a presentation consisting of 9-10 slides related to the topic;
- creating infographics based on materials related to the topic;
- development of appropriate tests on the Internet related to the topic (the subject teacher will provide the Internet sites of the relevant topics) and improve one's knowledge.

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